

Formulation of A New Strategy Based on Application of Swot Analysis and Quantitative Strategies Planning Matric at Smk Karya Ruteng

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the application of swot analysis and quantitative strategies planning matrices at SMK Karya Ruteng. These two things are nebeded as a contextual approach in reading the direction of the institution's development so that it can face all possible changes that will occur, carry out continuous monitoring, and conduct periodic evaluations. The researcher will present possible choices of action or alternative strategies for each decision by making this approach the basis. The purpose of this research is to identify strategic environmental factors in the development of SMK Karya Ruteng; determine the position and condition of SMK Karya Ruteng based on environmental factors; seek alternative strategies in the development of SMK Karya Ruteng; formulate strategic priorities in the development of SMK Karya Ruteng and formulate implementation strategies for developing SMK Karya Ruteng. This research was conducted qualitatively with interviews and observations conducted on the Principal and several appropriate resource persons at the SMK by Ruteng.

Keywords : New Strategy, SWOT Analysis, Quantitative Strategies Planning Matrix

Abstrak

Penelitian ini mengkaji penerapan analisis swot dan matriks perencanaan strategi kuantitatif di SMK Karya Ruteng. Kedua hal ini disandingkan sebagai pendekatan kontekstual dalam membaca arah perkembangan lembaga sehingga mampu menghadapi segala kemungkinan perubahan yang akan terjadi, melakukan monitoring secara terus menerus, dan melakukan evaluasi secara berkala. Peneliti akan menyajikan kemungkinan pilihan tindakan atau alternatif strategi untuk setiap keputusan dengan menjadikan pendekatan ini sebagai dasar. Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mengidentifikasi faktor-faktor lingkungan strategis dalam pengembangan SMK Karya

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Ruteng; menentukan posisi dan kondisi SMK Karya Ruteng berdasarkan faktor-faktor lingkungan; mencari alternatif strategi dalam pengembangan SMK Karya Ruteng; merumuskan prioritas strategi dalam pengembangan SMK Karya Ruteng; merumuskan prioritas strategi dalam pengembangan SMK Karya Ruteng dan merumuskan strategi implementasi pengembangan SMK Karya Ruteng. Penelitian ini dilakukan secara kualitatif dengan wawancara dan observasi yang dilakukan terhadap Kepala Sekolah dan beberapa narasumber yang sesuai di SMK Karya Ruteng.

Kata kunci : Strategi Baru, Analisis SWOT, Kuantitatif Matriks Perencanaan Strategi

PRELIMINARY

Strategic management has become a new basis in the world of management as well as the main tool for managerial decision making. With it, companies/organizations/institutions are able to reduce uncertainty and business complexity (David, Fred.2007). In another view, strategic management is used as a source of determinants of company goals which reads external factors-business environment (industrial environment, macro environment), Internal factors (functional management, corporate culture) refer to the company's goals, namely profit, stock prices, sales, and sales. survival (Suwarsono. 1996). This basis is also closely related to the strategic management component which affirms managerial efforts to develop the company's strength to exploit emerging business opportunities in order to achieve the company's goals that have been set in accordance with the specified mission. Therefore, business environment analysis is needed to detect business opportunities and threats, company profile analysis to identify company strengths and weaknesses, strategies used to achieve company goals by taking into account the company's mission,

In practice, the strategic components of the business are carried out in accordance with the sequence of the main management functions, namely planning, implementation, and supervision. Methodologically: formulation (formulation), implementation (execution), strategy monitoring, and feedback (providing input/evaluation). Strategic thinking in managing the company is very simple according to the business environment that influences it. If the Company does not often experience turbulence in its business dynamics, then strategic management is rarely used. Vice versa.

In simple terms, the four stages of strategic management development using time benchmarks in several developed countries are (1). Budgeting and Financial Monitoring (2) Long-Term Planning, (3) Corporate Strategic Planning, and (4) Strategic Management. In addition, Strategic Management Intensity puts emphasis on comprehensiveness, detail and accuracy, simple and partial (in small and medium-sized companies). A number of factors that influence it are the size of the organization, Management style, the complexity of the Business Environment, the production

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process, the characteristics of the problems encountered, and the purpose of the Planning. One of the main elements in strategic management is a strategic plan which, according to Porter, is a future projection of a business unit/business/company/institution/organization.

The above study needs to be placed on educational institutions as one of the business/business units that offer educational services to create quality and character graduates while at the same time earning profits that are useful for smooth operations and income for stakeholders. The elements of Strategic management as described above become a typical guide for the implementation of education based on an accurate strategic plan, right on target, and in accordance with the vision and mission of the foundation.

Specifically, this study looks at the management of the Karya Vocational High School Education Institution (hereinafter; SMK). The question that arises is whether the management is based on strategic management discourse? If so, how is it implemented? The researcher's attention focuses on the governance of institutions that substantially contribute/recommend management based on strategic management through strategic plans in the four indicators mentioned above.

Since its establishment, Ruteng's SMK has played an important role in building education in Manggarai district. Consistent educational dynamics and stable teaching staff are big assets to produce graduates from year to year. Of course, the integrity of the institution becomes stronger along with the

problems and achievements of the entire educational process that has been carried out. Like educational institutions in general, SMK Karya Ruteng also carries out management functions starting from learning planning, formulation of learning strategies, implementation, supervision, and evaluation. In addition to following the curriculum changes that have been set, it also follows the policies of YKM as the owner and coach of educational institutions (top management).

In fact, SMK Karya Ruteng has compiled an Annual School Work Plan (RKTS) for the 2017/2018, 2018/2019, and 2019/2024 school years. The RKTS is used as a working guide (frame of reference) for schools in developing schools, as a basis for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of school development and as a reference material for identifying and proposing educational resources needed for school development (RKTS SMK Karya.2019.5). In addition, the purpose of preparing the RKTS is for schools to know in detail the actions that must be taken so that the goals, obligations, and targets of school development can be achieved.

RKTS is a substantial matter based on Law No. 20 articles 8 and 48 of 2003 concerning the national education system, government regulations No. 19 articles 49 and 53 of 2005 concerning national education standards, Permendiknas No. 19 number 4a points 1 and 2 of 2007 Regarding Education Management Standards, and Kepmediknas 129a of 2004 concerning Service Standards in the Education Sector. By regulation, RKTS is a means required by the Government so that education always exists in a correct and appropriate system on a

national scale so that its targets are in line with the ideals of national education. Therefore, this RKTS needs to be prepared properly and correctly so that it is in accordance with regulations, national education visions and missions in general, and the Foundation's vision and mission in particular.

The preparation of the RKTS needs to be done by embedding standards based on a strategic management approach. Why?, there are two advantages to be gained. First, strategic management offers specific indicators by reading and mapping the macro and micro environmental conditions, external and internal schools. Second, Strategic management provides a variety of guidelines in preparing RKTS so that if read from a business perspective, RKTS can be a means of supporting the success of the School and gaining consistent sustainable markets and profits. Strategic Management through the three elements; The application of swot analysis, distinctive features of generic competitive strategies, and quantitative strategies planning matrix is a contextual approach so that it affirms all possibilities for change, continuous monitoring, and periodic evaluation. The researcher will present the possible choices of action from each decision by making the four elements as the basis.

Strategic Management is a strength for schools to construct all HR buildings as managers and providers of educational services in order to satisfy customers (students). A solid human resource building accompanied by careful planning, supervision, program implementation, and evaluation is a great hope that is able to provide high loyalty in students. Back to the

original question, is the implementation of SMK Karya Ruteng education in accordance with the RKTS? This answer will be answered throughout the body of this study. However, in the pre-survey period a number of problems were found. First, the implementation of RKTS has not been maximized. This is caused by at least two reasons, namely the school's structure, educators who do not understand the main tasks and functions and the inability to translate the RKTS into real action. Second,

The two problems above are signs that the RKTS has not been understood as something important, temporary and enforced under certain conditions or demands. The school has failed to carry out its dynamics even though everything that is needed can be obtained. The problems above implicitly illustrate that schools have not practiced strategic management in developing their education. If left unchecked, the consequences will clearly lead to mistakes in carrying out the main tasks and at worst losing the market. Through this research, researchers provide a reference and basis for thinking and acting for the school to really see RKTS as a learning guide so that it is always in accordance with the vision and mission. The specification of this research is to provide an understanding of the application of swot analysis,

The problems of SMK Karya in implementing its RKTS are system problems which are fundamentally regulatory and academic. When compared with the views of Porter and Fred R David, the application of swot analysis, distinctive features of generic competitive strategies, and quantitative strategies planning matrices, is a good start to

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overcome these problems. Porter and Fred R David present these elements in such a complex way that their application is not short-lived but rather broad and profound. The dynamics of SMK Karya Ruteng education so far have been running normally without the right combination of all elements, both foundations, educators, students and all employees. This fact is the antecedents of a plausible reason, namely the non-application of the elements of Strategic Management that will be described in this study.

The institution's internal conditions greatly determine the implementation of this strategic management element. Readiness and ability to plan and make up-to-date learning designs based on strategic management are needed so that the direction of the institution is in line with the vision and mission of the founders. Every element in the institution, both stakeholders, educators, must reduce sectoral and individual egos and together build a good education system. From the real conditions above, the researcher conducted a study entitled the application of swot analysis, distinctive features of generic competitive strategies, and quantitative strategies planning matrix at SMK Karya Ruteng.

Based on these problems, the objectives of this study are (1) to identify strategic environmental factors in the development of SMK Karya Ruteng; (2) Determine the position and condition of SMK Karya Ruteng based on environmental factors; (3) Looking for alternative strategies in developing SMK Karya Ruteng; (4) Formulating strategic priorities in the development of SMK Karya Ruteng and (5) Formulating the implementation of

development strategies for SMK Karya Ruteng.

Theoretical Review

There are several theories used in this study, namely, first, the SWOT Matrix. The SWOT matrix is a tool to formulate various alternative strategies that are applied. This analysis clearly illustrates the external opportunities and threats faced by the organization that can be adjusted to the strengths and weaknesses it has (David, 2006: 282-306 Matrix of International Factor Evaluation (IFE) and External Factor Evaluation (EFE). According to David (2006: 283) IFE and EFE which aims to analyze environmental factors, both internal and external to the institution. To determine the assessment of the weights of internal and external factors, the Paired Comparison technique is used. The determination of the weight of each variable is compared using a scale of 1, 2, and 3 (Kinnear & Taylor, 1991). Second, The Internal-External (IE) matrix is used to map the total score of the resulting IFE and EFE matrices.). The purpose of using the IE and SWOT matrices simultaneously is the IE matrix to show the position of an organization so that when formulating alternative strategies using the SWOT matrix, it remains to focus on the area where the organization is located where each region has different strategic implications. Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) or quantitative strategic planning matrix to show which alternative strategy is the best. QSPM uses input from stage one analysis and matching results from stage two analysis (David, 2006: 308-313). Some important things that must be done by institutions are setting annual goals,

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formulating policies, motivating workers and allocating resources (Hubeis & Najib, 2014:

Research Methods

This research was conducted using a qualitative approach. Sources of data were obtained from interviews with the Principal and several related sources, and in-depth observations of the SMK Karya Ruteng Educational Institution. The data obtained were analyzed and processed in such a way as to produce several important references for the development of the Karya Ruteng Vocational Education Institution. The data used in this study are primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained from internal and external data of the Institute, which was carried out by direct observation in the field as well as from the results of direct and in-depth interviews with school principals and teachers. Determination of respondents based on their position and level of mastery of the problems asked. Secondary data is in the form of the School Annual Work Plan (RKTS). Other data are obtained from journals, books, internet or other sources that are directly related to the problem and topic of this research. The method applied is David's (2006) structural framework because it applies over time and is the simplest way to achieve a strategic program (Yazdani, et al., 2012: 82).

Research Results and Discussion

SMK Karya Short Profile

SMK Karya Ruteng is one of the Vocational High Schools in Ruteng, which is located on Jl. Yos Sudarso No. 1 Langke Rembong District, Manggarai Regency, NTT. SMK Karya was established by the Karya

Manggarai Foundation and began operating in 1972. However, a decree for the establishment of a new school was issued on March 1, 1973 with the number 674/B.II/F/E/73. SMK Karya has three accredited skill programs, namely Accounting with accreditation B (good), Marketing accreditation B (good), and Office Administration with registered status (Operational permit) PPO Office number 420/750.a/V/2016.

In its dynamics, SMK Karya is guided by the Vision and Mission of the Institution. Its vision is "to make SMK Karya Ruteng an excellent educational institution in providing ready-to-work human resources and continuing to higher education levels" while its mission is to create an education and training system that is moral, cultured, independent, has an entrepreneurial spirit, is competency-based and is trusted by the community. . The vision and mission of SMK Karya is measured by the right indicators, namely encouraging optimal activity and creativity to all school components, especially students, optimizing learning in order to improve students' skills so that they have proud achievements,

Currently, SMK Karya has 895 students divided into three skill programs. The number of each class is as follows; class X as many as 304 people, Class XI as many as 294 people, and class XII as many as 297 people (Data for SMK.TA 2019/2024/August 2019). SMK Karya has 50 educators and education staff with details on the status of state teachers as many as 2 people, permanent teachers for foundations as many as 41 people, and administrative staff as many as 7 people.

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Goal Formula

The formulation of the objectives of the Karya Ruteng Vocational School is to obtain an average national exam score that meets graduation standards, have advanced extra-curricular activities and guarantee achievement in all fields, the realization of high discipline from all school components, the realization of an atmosphere of daily association based on faith and piety, the realization of transparent and participatory school management, involving all components of the school and related interest groups, and the realization of a clean, beautiful, safe and beautiful school environment

Competitive Advantage

The competitive advantages of SMK Karya Ruteng are as follows: Has three skill programs that are in high demand, Improves quality by developing online-based majors, Complete computer laboratory, Has a business unit as a place for students to practice, Strategic location.

SWOT SMK Karya Ruteng

SWOT describes the internal and external conditions of the Karya Ruteng Vocational School. SWOT mapping is based on all internal and external conditions that affect the dynamics of education. Based on the results of interviews with several resource

persons, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for SMK Karya Ruteng are as follows: Strengths: Competent teaching staff (HR), Has three expertise programs that are in great demand, Rules of educational institutions that are in demand maintain the stability of all components, B accredited, Have a good academic culture, There is an increase in teacher salaries, The number of students is 897 people, Cooperating with the Foundation. Weaknesses: Not all rules are implemented properly (attendance), there are still insufficient teaching staff, limited study space, inadequate school information health services. Opportunity: Obtaining school operational funding assistance (BOS), a clear market base, accepting students from all walks of life with competitive educational costs, a strategic school environment located in the city center, technological developments and advancements that provide convenience in institutional management and improve the quality of learning, Highly sought after skill program. Challenges: The demands of the increasingly complex world of work, curriculum changes, job demands

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Weights indicate the relative importance of a factor to business success in a company or organization. The weight of each factor is obtained by the value of each factor to the total factor value. Based on the SWOT formulation above, the weighting can be seen in table 1.1)

(Table 1.1 Internal Factors, Strengths and Weaknesses)

1. Internal Factors (Strengths and Weaknesses)

No	Power	Weight
1	Competent teaching staff (HR)	0.020
2	Has three skill programs that are in high demand	0.112
3	Rules of educational institutions that maintain the stability of all components	0.030
4	B credited	0.142
5	Have a good academic culture	0.022
6	There is an increase in teacher salaries	0.115
7	The number of students is 897 people	0.120
8	Collaborating with the Foundation	0.110
No	Weakness	
1	Not all rules are executed properly	0.112
2	Educators are still lacking	0.104
3	Limited study space	0.005
5	Inadequate school information access	0.008
	Total	1,000

2. External Factors (Opportunities and Threats)

No	Opportunity	Weight
1	Obtaining school operational financing assistance (BOS)	0.024
2	Clear market base	0.022
3	Accept students from all walks of life	0.064
4	Strategic school environment in the city center	0.147
5	Technological developments and advancements that provide convenience in institutional management and improving the quality of learning	0.023
6	Highly sought after skill programs	0.020
No	Challenge	
1	The demands of an increasingly complex world of work	0.180
2	Curriculum changes	0.165
3	Shaping the character of students	0.146
	Total	1,000

(Source of data; Processed by researchers. 2024)

Rating

(Table. 1.2 Rating)

1. Power

No	Power	Rating
1	Competent teaching staff (HR)	4
2	Has three skill programs that are in high demand	4
3	Rules of educational institutions that maintain the stability of all components	3
4	B credited	4
5	Have a good academic culture	3
6	There is an increase in teacher salaries	3
7	The number of students is 897 people	4
8	Collaborating with the Foundation	3

2. Weakness

No	Weakness	
1	Not all rules are executed properly	3
2	Educators are still lacking	3
3	Limited study space	3
5	Inadequate school information access	3

3. Opportunity

No	Opportunity	Rating
1	Obtaining school operational financing assistance (BOS)	4
2	Clear market base	3
3	Accept students from all walks of life	3
4	Strategic school environment in the city center	4
5	Technological developments and advancements that provide convenience in institutional management and improving the quality of learning	4
6	Highly sought after skill programs	3
4	Challenge	
No	Challenge	Rating
1	The demands of an increasingly complex world of work	4

2	Curriculum changes	3
3	Shaping the character of students	4

(Source; Processed by researchers.2024)

4. Internal Factor Evaluation Matrix Results

(Table 1.3 Results of Internal Factor Evaluation Matrix)

No	Internal factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Power				
1	Competent teaching staff (HR)	0.020	4	0.08
2	Has three skill programs that are in high demand	0.112	4	0.448
3	Rules of educational institutions that maintain the stability of all components	0.030	3	0.09
4	Certified B by decision	0.142	4	0.568
5	There is an increase in teacher salaries	0.022	3	0.198
6	The number of students is 897 people	0.115	4	0.46
7	Have a good academic culture	0.120	3	0.36
8	Collaborating with the Foundation	0.110	3	0.33
Total Strength Value				2,534
No	Internal factors		Rating	Score
Weakness				
1	Not all rules are executed properly	0.112	3	0.336
2	Educators are still lacking	0.104	3	0.312
3	Limited study space	0.005	3	0.015
4	Inadequate school information access	0.008	3	0.024
Total Weakness Score				0.687
Total Strengths and Weaknesses				3,221

(Source; Processed by researchers.2024)

Results of External Factor Evaluation (EFE) Analysis

(Table 1.4 Results of External Factor Evaluation Matrix)

No	External Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunity				
1	Obtaining school operational financing assistance (BOS)	0.024	4	0.096
2	Clear market base	0.022	3	0.066
3	Accept students from all walks of life with competitive tuition fees	0.064	3	0.192
4	Strategic school environment in the city center	0.147	4	0.588
5	Technological developments and advancements that provide convenience in institutional management and improving the quality of learning	0.023	4	0.092
6	Highly sought after skill programs	0.020	3	0.06
Total Opportunity Score				1.094
No	External Factors		Rating	Score
Challenge				
1	The demands of an increasingly complex world of education	0.180	4	0.72
2	Curriculum changes	0.165	3	0.495
3	Shaping the character of students	0.146	4	0.584
Total Challenge Score				1,799
Total Value of Opportunities and Challenges				2,893

IFE and EFE calculations are aligned with the average value of IFE and EFE calculations, which is 2.50. If you look at these results, the explanation is as follows: First, the total value of the strengths and weaknesses of SMK Karya Ruteng is 3,221. This result indicates that the value is above the mean of 2.50. It means that the human resources owned, accreditation, excellence of Study Programs, jointly implemented rules, increase in teacher salaries, number of students, academic culture, and collaboration

with foundations are above average in utilizing strengths and anticipating internal weaknesses. In other words regulations that are not implemented properly, teaching staff are still lacking, limited study space, and inadequate school information Askes can be complemented by maximizing the strengths they have. The human resources owned by SMK Karya can maximize the implementation of the rules properly (acting professionally), the teaching staff who are still not maximized by increasing the number

of teachers adjusted to the number of students and followed by the addition of classrooms so that learning demands can be met. Cooperation with the management (foundation) is also maximized so that operational, physical and non-physical needs can be met

From the results of the analysis of the calculation of external strategy factors, the total score was 2.893. This means that the EFE value is above the average of 2.50. This shows that SMK Karya has a strategy that can take advantage of opportunities and minimize external negative threats/influences, but still requires other more effective strategies because there are still external strategic factors that only SMK Karya responds on average. Getting help School operational costs (BOS), a clear market base, accepting students from all walks of life, a strategic school environment located in the city center, technological developments and advancements that provide convenience in institutional management and improving the

quality of learning, many skill programs interest can minimize existing threats.

IE Matrix

The positioning of the IE matrix strategy is based on the total value of the IFE matrix which is weighted on the x-axis and the total value of the EFE matrix on the x-axis.y. The average value of IFE and EFE is obtained from the sum of the scores on each factor, where the score is obtained from the multiplication between the average *rating* and the average weight on each factor. The total value of the IFE matrix is 3,221 and the EFE matrix value is 2,893. Thus the position of STIE Karya lies in quadrant IV, which shows the strategy that is needed at this time is to grow and build a strategy. SMK Karya needs a strategy to grow better and be able to develop a better institution. The strategies that can be applied by companies today are intensive strategies, integrative strategies, and concentration strategies.

IE Matrix Image

SWOT Matrix

The SWOT matrix produces several alternative strategies obtained from internal and external variables according to the company's position in the IE matrix, namely *Grow and build strategy*. The alternative strategies obtained are as follows:

<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">INTERNAL</div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">EXTERNAL</div>	<p>STRENGTH (S)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Competent teaching staff (HR) 2. Has three skill programs that are in high demand 3. Rules of educational institutions that maintain the stability of all components 4. Certified B by decision 5. There is an increase in teacher salaries 6. The number of students is 897 people 7. Have a good academic culture 8. Collaborating with the Foundation 	<p>WEAKNESS (W)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not all rules are executed properly 2. Educators are still lacking 3. Educators based on the ratio of teacher needs 4. Management of the use of BOS funds that have not been well planned 5. Inadequate access to school information
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<p>EXTERNAL</p> <p>OPPORTUNITY (O)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Obtain BOS funding assistance Bantuan 2. Clear market base 3. Accept students from all circles 4. Strategic school environment. be in the city center 5. The development and advancement of technology that facilitates the management of the board and improves the quality of learning 6. Health programs are in high demand 	<p>SO</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop three skill programs by utilizing BOS funds and good management of BOS funds 2. Develop a market base by utilizing competent educators 3. Tighten the rules of educational institutions by considering the location of the school environment in the city center 4. Maintaining a good academic culture by taking advantage of technological developments and advances 5. Maintaining the stability of cooperation with the Foundation in order to create quality institutional management (S1,01); (S4.02); (S7.04);(S8.05) 	<p>WO</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilize BOS funds to add study rooms 2. Increase the number of educators according to the ratio of needs in order to maintain the market base 3. Increase access to information in learning by reading developments and technological advances <p>(W1,01); (W3,05);(W4,05)</p>
<p>CHALLENGE (C)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The demands of an increasingly complex world of work 2. Curriculum changes 3. Forming the character of students 	<p>SC</p> <p>Utilizing competent educators, stable collaboration with foundations, accreditation of educational institutions, good academic culture to respond to the demands of an increasingly complex world of work, curriculum changes, and character building of students.</p> <p>(S1,C1); (S4,C2);(S7,C3);(S8,C3)</p>	<p>WC</p> <p>Responding to the demands of the world of work, curriculum changes and character building of students by carrying out the rules (discipline) well, increasing the ratio of educators, adding study spaces, and increasing access to school information</p> <p>(W1, C1); (W2, C2); (W3, C3)</p>

Quantitative Strategy Planning Matrix (QSPM)

SMK Karya needs to choose an appropriate strategy that can be implemented using QSPM. The QSPM analysis tool confirms the alternative strategies obtained from the SWOT matrix where the matrix produces several alternative strategies

through internal and external factors of the institution. The QSPM value is obtained intuitively by considering the possible strategies that can be chosen. Based on the interest seen in the SWOT Matrix, the alternative strategies chosen are intensive, integrative strategies, and

concentration strategies which refer to the alternative details as follows:

1. Develop three skill programs by utilizing financial assistance School Operations (BOS)
2. Develop a market base by utilizing competent educators
3. Tighten the rules of educational institutions by considering the location of the school environment in the city center
4. Maintaining a good academic culture by taking advantage of developments and technology advances
5. Maintaining the stability of cooperation with the Foundation in order to create institutional management quality one

Conclusion

The conclusions that can be drawn from this research are:

1. Based on the analysis of IFE and EFE, STIE Karya's position lies in quadrant IV, which shows the strategy that is needed at this time is to grow and build a strategy. SMK Karya needs a strategy to grow better and be able to develop a better institution. The strategies that can be applied by companies today are intensive strategies, integrative strategies, and concentration strategies.

2. The alternative strategy that can be taken is SO, namely Develop three skill programs by utilizing School Operational funding assistance (BOS), Developing a market base by utilizing competent educators, Tightening the rules of educational institutions by considering the location of the school environment in the city center, Maintaining a good academic culture by utilizing technological developments and advances, Maintaining the stability of cooperation with the Foundation in order to create quality institutional management

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